

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: AL-TAHER****FIRST NAME: AMMAR****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%, No AI-generated text detected

The author used the following software: MSWord10 on Windows11

List your 5-7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP):

1. Academic Essay (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 6–14)
2. American vs. British English (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 24–32)
3. Plagiarism and AI-generated text (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 33–39)
4. Citation (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 33–39)
5. Chicago Style (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 40–57)

RESPONSE PAPER WRITING GUIDELINES

1) INTRODUCTION

ACA-40101D roadmap presentation by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma provides, as the name implies a roadmap for getting started, including the use of the Course Management (CMS) and the Learning Management System (LMS) as well as an overview of the requirement for course completion. It provided the steps for writing and sending the response papers and quizzes.

The orientation email sent by the admission office provided similar information relating to CMS and LMS, including paper samples and templates. It also stated that the primary goal of the ACA-401D course is to become familiar with EUCLID's way of doing things.

The welcome email by the course instructor, Dr. Kabiru Gulma, further provides details on course objectives to help us master paper wiring, including the use of information technology tools such as Zotero software and Grammarly, as well as appropriate referencing styles, use of US or UK English, and the appropriate use of the Response (RP) template. Dr. Gulma also included links to download relevant documents and videos.

The Student Orientation Document “Print and Keep on Hand” details how to get students started. It provides more details than the presentation on response papers, creating a quiz paper, major paper, oral examination, and protected quizzes. It also presents additional material relating to plagiarism.

Period one material out of the EMS includes two documents. One is the coursepack, and the other is the response paper template.

The following are some discussion points based on the provided coursepack.

2)ACADEMIC ESSAY

The first chapter of the course pack focuses on the importance of understanding the basics and the steps involved. The Academic essay is nonfictional writing produced as a part of academic work (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 7). It seeks to provide fact-based answers to a hypothesis.

It is essential to start early and have enough time to read, research, think, and write. It is also essential to have a plan to guide reading and research.

The chapter provides details from researching the topic, organizing ideas, and writing the essay, including referencing and editing.

The chapter continues by presenting guidelines for writing a paper, including stating the central thesis in the beginning, being specific and clear, and citing references, among other rules of thumb.

3)AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

American English is considered the most common variant of the English language used in academic writing due to the size, population, economy, and political state of the United States (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 25).

Chapter three provides different categories of differences between American and British English. Both variants are acceptable for academic writing, though consistency is critical.

4)PLAGIARISM AND AI-GENERATED TEXT

Plagiarism is taboo in academic writing as it implies taking others’ work or ideas.

Plagiarism is “when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information” (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 34). It is

wrong and unethical as it is not fair to take someone else's work without giving them credit for it.

Using the emerging Artificial Intelligence (AI)-generated text such that CHAT GPT poses an additional challenge. The online version of Grammarly can also detect the percentage of the text generated by AI, though it is not decisive.

5) CHICAGO STYLE

A style guide is a way to have a writing style consisting in terms of sentence length, manuscript layout, font usage, depth of treatment of the subject, spelling, use of abbreviations, accepted terminology, the use of symbols, voice preferences (active v passive), structure, paragraph numbering, and indentation, the use of headings, the use of lists and trademark or branding considerations among other (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 25).

EUCLID uses the Chicago Rules (Turabian) and American English. The provided templates, such as the response paper and primary paper templates, are already formatted according to the required Chicago rules, which makes it very convenient to get started and become proficient with time.

6) CITATION

Citation is a way to prevent plagiarism by giving credit to the author or the source of the information.

There are different ways to cite, including in-text citations such as quotations and paragraphs and a list of work cited such as footnote referencing and biographies.

All papers must include Turabian-style citations generated using Zotero software.

7) CONCLUSION

After some time and effort, the assignment for the first period became apparent to get us started in the EUCLID learning and writing journey for producing the best quality ethical academic writing. Academic essay writing is one of the focuses of this course and the whole education process at EUCLID.

I noticed some redundancy in the provided material and communication, but this should be fine. I learned and incorporated some of the features with this response paper and hope to use more features in the coming response paper.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 5th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.